

INFORMATION MANAGEMENT OF COVID-19 PANDEMIC AND ITS IMPLICATIONS ON PUBLIC HEALTH IN AKWA IBOM STATE

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Abstract

The Covid-19 pandemic has generated shocks that has caused economic fluctuations globally, calling for an understanding of the behaviour of macroeconomic and health variables. This study presents an early review of the information management and health impact of the Covid-19 pandemic on the residents of Akwa Ibom state. The aggregate supply and aggregate demand (AS-AD) model provides the theoretical motivation for the study. From the findings, while the number of infected cases reflects significant correlations with economic activity from the perspective of a trend analysis, the estimates from dynamic ordinary least squares (DOLS) shows that the nexus between the number of confirmed cases and attendant macroeconomic outcomes are largely insignificant with the expected signs. The study has therefore shown that the Covid-19 pandemic has insignificant negative impacts on basic macroeconomic variables in Akwa Ibom state and Nigeria in general such as inflation, employment, exchange rate, GDP growth, among others. In other words, time is required before the established correlations withstand empirical scrutiny in terms of causality. As the government has engaged the Economic Sustainable Plan (ESP, 2020), which is a post-Covid-19 recovery plan, it is hoped that the attendant policies would be properly implemented so as to provide the critical mass to repositioning the country's economy on the path towards inclusive and sustained economic development.

Introduction

Coronaviruses are potentially single-stranded enveloped viruses with an RNA that measures about 26 to 32kb. All coronaviruses that infect humans are zoonotic,

with bats being a primary reservoir for most of them. The 21st century has witnessed the incidences of three coronavirus outbreaks, with the latest being the coronavirus disease of 2019, also known as the COVID-19. The outbreak of the Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome coronavirus (SARS-COV) in 2003 resulted in 8096 cases globally with 774 deaths, while the Middle East Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus (MERS-COV) resulted in 2500 cases with 860 deaths. On the backdrop of the above phenomenon, the emergence of a new coronavirus disease has raised great Public Health concerns and may prove to have scathing global socioeconomic consequences in the long run, if the pandemonium continued to run its full course unhindered by robust Public Health intervention strategies that are dependable and sustainable.

Nonetheless, it is no longer breaking news that COVID-19 has shut down the world everyday activities in all spheres of lives. The highly infectious and very deadly virus has eroded the real meaning of humanity, which revolves around the fact that man is a social animal as espoused by Aristotle.

The relationship which hitherto existed between different people in the society and brings about social bonding has been drastically reduced, as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic and the world remains in constant increasing panic till date. The world is shaking, countries fighting individually and collectively to defeat what could be regarded as one of the greatest challenges, that has ever confronted mankind. It has revolted against social, economic, religious, political, cultural and academic gathering, among others.

The pandemic has fought both powerful and non-powerful countries. It has also killed both the wealthy and the poor masses in significant numbers to the abashed and worry of the rich and poor nations. COVID-19 pandemic was first reported in Wuhan, located in the Hubei province of China in early December, outcome. The origin of COVID-19 outbreak has been linked to a Huanan Seafood market in China that deals with the sale of live animals; this strongly suggests likelihood of zoonotic infection supposedly links to the viral pandemic outcome.

However, several conspiracy theories exist as regards to the origin of the virus, with some speculations of the virus being a biological weapon from China, amid many other unsubstantiated claims especially those linked with the 5G network being developed from China. Despite these speculations and accusations, the world has been gripped by the novel virus which has now caused 989 thousand deaths across 193 countries, regions and territories, while 12 countries are yet to record a single case.

Therefore, the World Health Organisation, regional and local health bodies have adopted measures to stop the further spread of the disease, and has also tasked the public and the leadership of various countries to enforce the measures necessary to limit the spread of the virus such as social distancing, regular hand washing, lockdown and closing of borders. In Nigeria, President Muhammadu Buhari in

two successive broadcasts to the nation ordered a lockdown of certain parts of the country such as Abuja, Lagos and Ogun State. Mr Buhari also ordered the restriction of human and vehicular movements across the country. Consequently, several countries are already grappling with the deleterious effects of the measures set up to combat COVID-19 in various spheres of their socio-economic existence of many countries by considerably halting the economic activities in these countries.

According to a study on the impact of COVID-19 lockdown in Sub-Saharan Africa carried out by Teachout, et al. it was reported that 9.1% of the population has fallen into extreme poverty, with 65% of this being due to the lockdown, and about 30% of the total population have exhausted their savings, which incapacitates them from responding to future shocks. In Nigeria, the federal government sent a revised budget to the National Assembly due to constant drop in crude oil prices, and thereby revised the budget proposal revenue projection for the 2020 fiscal period by a difference of N3.3 trillion naira from the initially approved amount of 8.41 trillion naira to 5.08 trillion naira.

Meanwhile, amid the partial lockdown of the country, economic activities at the macro and micro levels have been grounded, while social activities are also halted. The above situations have forced governments, both at the state and federal levels to put in place some palliative measures to cushion the effects on the masses and businesses. At the centre of it all is the increasingly public health risk or concern, which this study seeks to provide answers to.

The novel coronavirus has taken its grip on Nigeria economy and her citizens, forcing the federal government to declare partial lockdown in Lagos, Ogun and Abuja and restriction of vehicular and human movements across the country. These measures are aimed at curtailing the further spread of the virus, even as 36 states of the federation have recorded cases of the virus bringing the number of cases in the country to 58 thousand with over Ithousand+ deaths as at 25th Sept 2020 with Akwa Ibom state having about over 200 cases with 8 deaths. The measures have affected social and economic situations across the country. Consequently, several wedding ceremonies have been cancelled while most economic activities have also been halted. These situations have affected both low and high-income earners in various businesses.

More so, traders and transporters have been affected while religious activities are now being conducted mostly on the internet and only those who can afford to buy data and smart phones are those favoured while the poorest poor in the country could not get involved in online worshipping. The overall impact of these situations is on Public Health wellbeing, hence ban on social gathering and introduction of social distancing approach in human social interaction was very strange in this part of the world. However, governments at the federal, state and the grassroot levels have not provided tangible palliatives to the masses, to cushion the effects on the

people which have made most people who live from hand to mouth to ignore the preventive measures in pursuit of food at the detriment of Public Health protection strategies.

The objectives of this study are, therefore, to ascertain (i) the impact of COVID-19 pandemic on the federal government of Nigeria with respect to the trend of governance (ii) To analyse and evaluate the brunt of COVID-19 pandemic on businesses in Nigeria. (iii) To analyse the effect of COVID 19 pandemic on socio-economic activities on the citizens of Akwa Ibom state especially, with those on the daily income earners, across the state.

However, it is strongly believed that information generated from this study would promote government and other relevant health agencies to plan towards providing sustainable and dependable palliative measures to cushion the socio-economic impact of COVID 19 pandemic on the citizens.

2.0 Information management system of Covid19 pandemic

Given the speed at which the COVID-19 pandemic has emerged and disseminated, we believe that information systems researchers can now play a key role. Who would be better suited to critically appraising the extent to which current technologies and use of those technologies can help overcome this crisis in the short term, and also examine how best we can utilise technology to recover in the long term? As the COVID-19 pandemic affects the very nature of life as we know it, there are many themes and research angles that relate to information systems and present opportunities for our researchers to contribute. To provide some food for thought, let us discuss a few of these.

The centrality of information in the COVID-19 disaster: A review of media coverage reveals that it is information and information systems that are fueling and facilitating our response to the COVID-19 pandemic, affecting a wide range of stakeholders. Data analysis and forecasting underpin government policy and decision making, and it is the ongoing analysis that is providing governments with information as to the efficacy and impact of these policies and decisions. People have seen their lives fundamentally change overnight. The general public has now become amateur data scientists consuming endless analyses, summaries and graphs as a source of solace and comfort. People need to make sense of the unfolding pandemic and to understand the impact it may have on them, their livelihood, their family and friends. Almost everyone is familiar with some variant of infection and death rate visualisation, and the constant strive to "flatten the curve". Information in various, crude and often rudimentary forms is what businesses and financial institutions are using to make some sense of the new climate and liquid context that each finds themselves in. Information systems can contribute to all of these areas by examining the specific role of information and information systems across and between the various stakeholders.

Determining what constitutes information systems value and success in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic: In order to examine how successful a particular technology is in aiding the fight against COVID-19, it is necessary to understand what constitutes "value". Comprehensively defining and capturing the value of a system is usually very challenging, as it often manifests in many multi-dimensional and polymorphous, ephemeral ways (Schryen, It manifests in 2013). ways that are hard to measure with quantitative indicators, and there is often a significant time lag between the implementation of the system and the resulting value (Schryen, 2013). What constitutes value is often inextricably tied to the context of use and is usually multi-faceted. An analysis of what should constitute value in the case of COVID-19 shows there are many polymorphous and often contradictory measures, most of which have perceived strengths and weaknesses. For example, a directive to lock down a nation will, on the one hand, most likely reduce the number of cases but will have a detrimental impact on measures of the economy and societal issues such as education and mental health. There are several metrics used to assess the COVID-19 situation, including:

the number of COVID-19 infectious patients with symptoms,
the number of COVID-19 infections in patients without symptoms,
COVID-19 hospital admission in the general population,
COVID-19 patients moved to Intensive Care Unit (ICU) (or described as "severe"),
COVID-19 patients progressed from "severe" to "critical", and
COVID-19 deaths or mortality rate.

Certainly, metrics like these raise many questions, such as: How relevant are these metrics concerning information systems value and success? Can digital artefacts and practices contribute to improving these measures and metrics? How can metrics like these be used to inform and evaluate information system designs?

Examining the behavioural, temporal, societal, and organisational aspects of the pandemic: Technology is playing a central role in many if not all aspects of the COVID-19 pandemic. We rely on technology to help find a cure, to keep supply chains functioning and to allow businesses to find new ways of working during the unprecedented upheaval. However, it is often the behavioural, societal and organisational aspects of these technologies and their use that will define ultimate success in this pandemic battle, and it is these aspects rather than the technologies themselves that are often the most challenging. Understanding the role of artificial intelligence and machine learning in COVID-19 related digital practices is a current critical example of this challenge (Ågerfalk, 2020). Temporality is a related timely example. Time is playing a central and pivotal role across many aspects of the COVID-19 pandemic. Our lives are all affected over an unknown period. In terms of interventions implemented by government officials, it is 'not the interventions

themselves that are up for debate but the timing of the introduction and lifting of these interventions. Essentially all of the core metrics used to measure the spread and devastation of the pandemic are time-oriented (e.g., new cases per day, deaths per day, number admitted to ICU per day, three and five-day rolling averages of each, the overall trends by week and month). It is these metrics that each government's actions are judged on, and it is these that each population looks to for reassurance. However, time is an inherently complex, multi-faceted, subtle concept and is, by nature, socially embedded. Failure to acknowledge and address these complex nuances usually renders analysis inaccurate and incomplete. Information systems researchers have traditionally been slow to address the polymorphous, complex and nuanced nature of time in their research (Saunders & Kim, 2007; Shen et al., 2015; Nandhakumar, 2002). Recent research also highlights the specific and exacerbated nature of temporal complexity in the context of big data (Conboy et al., 2018, 2019). This complexity is particularly concerning in the context of COVID-19, where so many are basing their decisions on big data analytics. Researchers can now examine the temporal complexities in a COVID-19 context and can determine how this complexity impacts how we think and judge the use of technologies as a solution.

The negative role of information systems in the COVID-19 pandemic: We must also acknowledge that the role of information systems in the COVID-19 crisis is not always a positive one, and technology and its misuse can have detrimental effects. The efficacy of various COVID-19 screening and testing technology is being questioned. Over-reliance on technology such as face masks and COVID-19 tracing apps can have negative behavioural implications as people let their guard down and reduce adherence to social distancing and other preventative measures. Of particular relevance to information systems research are, for instance, new openings for cybercrime and the spread of misinformation and fake news through social media. Concerns like these have led to the WHO Director-General stating we are fighting an infodemic as much as an epidemic (Zarocostas, 2020). Tackling the COVID-19 infodemic has been established as a research priority in the WHO response strategy (WHO, 2020), which has resulted in WHO's Myth Busters webpage_and Stop The Spread campaign.

Empirical Facts about the Covid-19 Pandemic in Nigeria and Akwa Ibom as the case study

Nigeria recorded its first case of Covid-19 on the 27th of February, 2020 and Akwat Ibom state had its first case in April with 5 cases as the index case. This index cases was imported case by a resident that travelled back from Lagos State. Consequent upon this and in consonance with the measures taken across the world, the state took various measures to contain the spread of the Covid-19 pandemic and these included: full or partial lockdowns, testing, contact tracing, case isolation, among others.

Leveraging on previous disaster management and containment skills such as the handling of the Ebola virus that broke out between 2014 and 2016, the state instituted a proportional response by constituting a Task Force (TF) which was saddled with the responsibility of managing the government response to the pandemic. A summary of the macroeconomic policies undertaken by the government to insulate the economy from the impact of the pandemic is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Key Economic policy of the Nigerian and Akwa Ibom state government as at August 2020	
Policy category	N984 million contingency fund released to Nigeria's center for disease control (NCDC).
Description	N6.5billion released for the purchase of testing kits, opening isolation centers and training medical personnel. Lagos State got a grant of N10billion to increase capacity for containing the outbreak. Review of 2020 Budget and a cut in capital spending by N1.5trillion. Provision of N500billion fiscal stimulus package (styled Covid-19 Intervention Fund) to support healthcare facilities, provide relief for tax payers and incentive to employers.
Fiscal	Introduction of Import duty waivers for pharmaceutical firms. Regulated fuel prices have been reduced, and an automatic fuel price formula introduced to ensure fuel subsidies are eliminated. Increase of the social register by 1 million households to 3.6 million to help cushion the effect of the lockdown.
Monetary and macro-financial	Maintenance of current monetary policy rate (MPR) by the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) in March. Additional measures introduced include. Reduction of interest rates on all applicable CBN interventions from 9 to 5 percent. Introduction of one-year moratorium on CBN intervention facilities. Creation of a N50 billion targeted credit facility. Injection of 3.6 trillion liquidity into the banking system; N100 billion to health sector, N2 trillion to the manufacturing sector, and N1.5 trillion to the real sector to impact industries. N1 trillion support to the agriculture sector to prevent food shortages. Introduction of regulatory forbearance to restructure loans in impacted sectors. N120 billion private sector special intervention initiative targeted at fighting Covid-19. Receipt of N42.6 billion in April, including \$50 million grant from the European Union. Establishment of Nigeria Solidarity and Support Fund to raise \$50 million to support physical infrastructure of healthcare centers in Local Governments and existing Social Investment Program.
Exchange rate and Balance of payment	Adjustment of the official exchange rate by 15 percent. Ongoing unification of various exchange rates under the investors and exporters (I&E) window, Bureau de Change, and retail and wholesale windows. The authorities committed to let the I&E rate move in line with market forces, and it has so far depreciated by about 4 percent. A few pharmaceutical companies have been identified to ensure they can receive FX and naira funding. The CBN has resumed FX supply in some other windows because I&E window turnover has been low since April

Source: Imf policy tracker (2020)

Residents of Akwa Ibom state has been severely affected by the spread of Covid-19 and the associated sharp decline in oil prices. As a commodity-exporting and resource-dependent nation, the pandemic widened the fiscal deficits in the country because of government proportional responses. Government spending and the susceptibility to high public debt vulnerabilities also increased.

Thus, the state demanded for financial assistance from federal government and private donors in order to cushion plausible effects of the pandemic (World Bank, 2020). The major economic damages of the pandemic in Akwa Ibom state are reflected in the falling development index, such as manufacturing index and fixed investment. The aggressive containment measures yielded positive results as the total confirmed cases of Covid-19 in Akwa Ibom state within the first 4 months were about 200 cases with just about 0.1% fatality rate.

Nevertheless, it became apparent that Nigeria could no longer afford a total lockdown because the damage caused by the pandemic was already perceptible in most sectors of the Nigerian economy. The most vulnerable sectors are the manufacturing sector and the service sector such as education, distribution, among others. More over in recent times the spread of the virus has decreased drastically with the state recording about 2% cases per day.

2.2 Lock Down and Curfew

In a move to combat the spread of the pandemic disease, President Muhammadu Buhari directed the cessation of all movements in Lagos and the FCT for an initial period of 14 days, which took effect from 11 pm on Monday, 30th March 2020. which took effect from Saturday, 2nd May 2020, at 9 am.

On Monday, 29th June 2020 the federal government extended the second phase of the eased lockdown by 4 weeks and approved interstate movement outside curfew hours with effect from July 1, 2020. Also, on Monday 27th July 2020, the federal government extended the second phase of eased lockdown by an additional one week.

On Thursday, 6th August 2020 the federal government through the secretary to the Government of the Federation (SGF) and Chairman of the Presidential Task Force (PTF) on COVID-19 announced the extension of the second phase of eased lockdown by another four (4) weeks.

3.0 Literature Review

The literature on the economic effect of Covid19 is no longer scant because from all indications, the cases are decreasing though, some parts of the world still record increase in cases. A good premise to start the review, therefore is to glean a similar incidence from a historical perspective. studies on the economic consequences of infectious diseases date back to 1918 the 19 Spanish Influenza. In retrospect, the Great Influenza provides the primordial premise for the study of the macroeconomic consequence of the Covid 19 pandemic.

The past epidemic sheds light on the economic costs especially in the presence or absence of stringent containment policies. Basic macroeconomic consequence of past pandemics such as 1918 Influenza included: (1) low sales due to customers sentiment. (ii) high cost to the service sector since they are most affected by facemask and social economic activities, among others distancing, and (iii) strain on (Boissay and Rungcharoenkitkul, 2020; Barro et al.

Studies also exist on the macroeconomics of recent viruses such as HIV/AIDS (1993), SARS (2003), Avian influenza (2003/19) and Ebola (2014), among others. For instance, the HIV/AIDS virus has been found to have significant direct and indirect economic consequences on all the economic agents. This correspondingly disrupted livelihood individual households, firms and government s, reduced labour supply, limited the level of labour productivity and output and increased provision for social security, among others. Until the development of the antiretroviral therapies which reduced the vulnerabilities of carriers and their life spans, various countries had to bear the economic costs of this virus, (Cuddington, 1993a; Mckibbin and Fernando, 2020).

Lee and McKibbin, (2004) estimated resulted into about 0. the global economic costs of SARS and found that it 1% loss in global GDP while Hai et al. (2004) assessed the short-term impact of SARS on the Chinese economy and

showed that it lowered the GDP growth by percent. Furthermore, Burns et al. (2006) evaluated the economic consequences of 12 avian, influenza and found that it resulted into about 0.1 percent and 4 percent loss in global GDP and Asia respectively. The economic consequence of predominant the Ebola epidemic, a virus in the West African region, was the focus of World Bank Report (2014). The estimates of the computer general equilibrium (CGE) model showed that the Ebola virus lowered the GDP in Guinea, Liberia and Sierra Leone by about 2.1 percent, 3.4 percent respectively, within the first year of the pandemic.

Boissay and Rungcharoenkitkul (2020) did an early review of the macroeconomic effect of Covid 19 using the US data, most especially relative to past pandemic macroeconomic consequences of past epidemics such as the 1918s. Basic 19 Influenza, SARS (2003), H5N1 avian influenza (2003 pandemic include:19), Ebola (201416) and the present Covid19 fall in GDP growth and decline in manufacturing production activities among others. They found that the economic cost of the Covid19 pandemic can be proxied by GDP foregone, most especially based on the comparison between the current GDP forecast and the Covid19 outlook. In the light of the April 8th U.S data, the study estimated that Covid19 would lead to output loss which ranged between 5-9 percent for the United States and between 4 and 4.5 percent for the global economy. The study recommended that a better understanding of the transmission channel of the Covid19 shock to the economy, the interaction between economic decisions and the pandemic and the policy trade off would assist in reducing the macroeconomic effect of the pandemic.

From a pessimistic perspective, Fornaro and Wolf (2020) modelled the impact of on macroeconomic policy in order to assess the macroeconomic implications of the pandemic. They asserted that Covid19 would cause a negative supply shock to the world economy by forcing factories to shut down and disrupting global supply chain (OECD 2020). The virus also depressed the global demand. They found that corona virus caused a fall in demand and involuntary unemployment. Social distancing impaired the ability of household to spend.

KPMG (2020) examined the economic impact of Covid19 in Nigeria. Findings revealed that the pandemic in Nigeria has a twin shock on the Nigerian oil dependent economy, namely, global and domestic shocks as well as oil price shock.

4.0 COVID-19 as a Public Health concern

Turnock, et al. views Public Health as a collective effort to identify and address the unacceptable realities that result in preventable and avoidable health outcomes, and it is the composite of efforts and activities that are carried out by people committed to these end. Also, the Institute of Medicine, conceptualized Public Health as the science and art of preventing diseases, prolong life, promoting health and efficiency through organised community effort. According to Donald Acheson, Public Health was defined as the science and art of preventing disease, prolonging life and promoting health through the organized efforts of society. This implies that the goal of Public Health in the period of the pandemic is bordered around the prevention of the spread of the disease, as well as how the socio-economic impacts and consequences of the pandemic affect the spread of the virus and the quality of lives.

The major response in limiting the spread of the COVID-19 pandemic involves methods that enable the application of social distancing such as lockdowns, travel restrictions, quarantine and self-isolation. The restrictions placed on human and vehicular movements by the federal and state governments are aimed at preventing further spread of the coronavirus, which is the one of the ways to eliminate the virus. It shows that the virus has continued to affect Public Health and has raised whole lot of massive concern from the government and the citizens point of view of such an emerging danger are abound in our collective society.

This has greatly affected various sectors of the economy, Public Health and human livelihood. In the healthcare sector, the risk to healthcare workers continue to increase as they have to face the chance of contracting the virus as they carry out their daily routine duty. Factors such as increasing cost of healthcare, lack of protective equipment, low number of intensive care unit beds and ventilators continue to expose the inadequacies of the healthcare sector, especially in the COVID-19 pandemic era.

This call for a great public health concern, as many individuals may not be able to bear the high cost of healthcare in the event of infection. The pharmaceutical sector has also suffered some setbacks due to difficulty in procuring pharmaceutical ingredients by pharmaceutical companies.

5.0 Health implications of Covid19 and it's empirical analysis

The world is no longer buzzing with sports, tourism, orchestra, religious fiesta and other cheering activities. The Public Health measures aimed at limiting the spread of COVID-19 has largely influenced the various aspects of social human

interaction, as well as all sectors of the economy such as the primary sectors (responsible for extracting raw materials), secondary sectors (responsible for the production of the finished product) and the tertiary sectors (all service providers). It has also greatly affected social and familial interactions with reduced interactions among friends and social groups. However, more disturbing is the increasing reports of domestic and sexual abuse due to lockdown and quarantine with reports of a 25% increase in calls to help-lines on domestic abuse.

The most affected primary sectors of the COVID-19 pandemic are the Petroleum and oil industry, as well as the agricultural industry. There has been an increased need for agricultural products, due to increased panic buying with a lower yield of products. The petroleum and oil industry as well suffered some major setbacks initially due to trade disagreements between Saudi Arabia and Russia leading to a great fall in the price of oil. The ban on movement and travelling also affected the consumption of petroleum products. In Nigeria, due to the drop in oil price, the budget review proposal has been sent to the Senate for approval, with a 39% slash in the original budget.

The manufacturing sectors were badly hit in the pandemic; due to lockdown and quarantine rules as working from home is not a feasible option for this aspect of the economy and limitations in importation being a barrier, especially in countries like Nigeria whose manufacturing industries are hugely dependent on the importation of raw materials especially from China. A reduction of 1.2% production is predicted in the global chemical industry; their worst growth since the financial crash of 2008.

The tertiary sector such as the education sectors, finance sectors, hospitality and tourism sectors, sports industry, media and information industry, real estate and housing industry and so on continue to feel the brunt of the pandemic outbreak. Closure of all schools including primary, secondary and tertiary institutions is one of the major recommendations advised to limit the spread of COVID-19, as school gathering has been proven to be a major means of disease spread during outbreaks. The United Kingdom was estimated to lose 3% of its gross domestic product due to school closure. This correlates with the model study which showed that closure of schools for four weeks will cost the state of New York in the United State 1.1 billion dollars and a nationwide school closure will cause a loss of 1% of the country's gross domestic product. While most advanced nations are developing the use of new technology such as e-learning platforms, such cannot be fully implemented in Nigeria, due to the divide in the educational system whereby certain services cannot be accessed by people in poor rural settings and some in urban settings.

COVID-19 outbreak has hurt businesses, the financial market and global financial economy generally, due to uncoordinated international governmental responses causing disarray in the international supply chain. Lockdown and self-isolation significantly reduced production, demand and consumption of certain goods and services. According to Olisah, et al., the Nigerian businesses affected most are the start-ups and small scale enterprises, consultancy, hospitality and aviation sectors. The tourism, hospitality and aviation sectors are arguably the biggest losers in the COVID-19 outbreak era.

The World Travel and Tourism Council has estimated that over 50 million jobs may be lost globally due to the COVID-19 pandemic, and the sector faces a great risk in that regard with great consequences as the tourism sector accounts for 10% of the World's gross domestic product. The aviation sector is struggling with unprecedented losses as various travel bans have been placed, with only highly essential travels allowed. Some airlines have asked for bailout funds to enable their sustainability, with UK airlines asking for 7 billion Euros. The Asset Management Corporation of Nigeria (AMCON) has also called out for bailout funds for Nigerian airlines to prevent a shutdown of the aviation sector.

The sports industry as well saw a major halt in activities with postponement and cancellation of major local and international sporting competitions due to COVID-19 pandemic as large gatherings in stadia and other sports facilities could be a potent means for the spread of the virus [50,60]. However, the information and research industry has experienced an upsurge as various research bodies and institutions such as The Coalition for Epidemic Preparedness Innovations (CEPI), are leading various efforts to develop vaccines and treatment regimens against the COVID-19 pandemic, having been backed and sponsored by large companies and corporations such as the Gate's Foundation, Welcome and Master card who have donated several millions of dollars to the efforts being made in the research field.

While religious gatherings may not be classified as a sector of the economy, religious activities play a significant role in the aspect of social, psychological and spiritual wellbeing of those who partake in it. The COVID-19 pandemic has also had a significant impact on religious gatherings, even as gathering of such magnitude tends to be a potent means of the viral spread. Thus guidelines such as regulated numbers of worshippers have been placed on most religious institutions, while those unable to partake due to these regulations can worship online. While the economic impacts of the ban on religious gathering are not determined, the negative social impact has been tremendously enormous on the overall livelihood of existence of the citizens across the globe.

However, a particular factor which is usually important in Public Health discourses, especially in light of the preventative measures and the socio-economic impact of these measures is the mental health of individuals involved. Public Health emergencies affect the people and might lead to fear, insecurity, stigma due to disease, loss of jobs, economic losses and so on and may lead to certain psychiatric conditions such as depression. This agrees with a study carried out by Brooks, et al. in which it was shown that people who have been in quarantine are likely to experience post quarantine stress syndrome. This also agrees with the work carried out by Wu, et al. after the SARS outbreak showed that patients and some hospital employees suffer from post quarantine stress and some lasted for as long as three years after the outbreak. Also, quarantine of health workers usually results in avoidance syndrome, thereby creating a phobia for approaching patients. Some quarantine stressors were outlined as long period of quarantine, fears of cross-infection, frustration and boredom, shortage of supplies and poor flow of information, while post quarantine stressors majorly involves lack or loss of finances and the stigma associated with quarantine.

It is therefore pertinent to set up measures which will mitigate post quarantine stressors. Thus, these critical aspects of Public Health engagement is literally lacking in developing communities like Nigeria, and probably in other Sub-Sahara African countries, even as there are visible lack of functioning health care facilities especially in the rural communities, which has remained a huge source of concern in this period of frustration and high wave of crime in our communities, due to hunger and potential poverty created by COVID 19 pandemic the need to consciously work very hard and diligently by government and other relevant stakeholders in health service delivery to correct the visible lack of clinical infrastructure in Nigeria would help in this direction. These would therefore, improve the overall Public Health wellbeing of the general masses in the country.

Conclusion

The outbreak of the pandemic has taken its toll on the socio-economic aspect of the world, as well as it has also affected every other aspect of human life. Despite the measures taken, there is continuous increase in the number of cases and deaths associated with COVID-19. The Nigerian government and concerned organizations and individuals are battling to contend these cases. The World Health Organization had been speaking on the need to increase efforts by African Governments to contend the virus due to the poor situation of health care in Africa.

Amidst these efforts, markets, schools, churches and other public places have been shut down and remain so closed. These has increased the sufferings of many Nigerians who are largely poor. But due to the precarious nature of the virus, governments at all levels have appealed to the masses to be patient though without

tangible and sustainable palliatives for the most vulnerable Nigerians amidst the country's poverty index. However, because COVID-19 is a Public Health disease, concerns for the safety of individuals and the entire masses remain the revolving point of discourse.

Therefore, based on the objectives for this study and from the various works of literature reviewed, COVID-19 pandemic has impacted negatively on the Akwa Ivom State government, forcing it to review its budget and spending. Meanwhile, the study has ascertained that businesses (large and small, corporate or not) have been greatly affected, making some Organizations to reduce the workforce, while some had threatened to do the same. This may increase the rate of crime and other problems in Akwa Ibom State and Nigeria at large.

On the individual level, COVID-19 has affected income generation and earning, which has impacted negatively on families. The mental health of many individuals are also of immense concern due to the stressors associated with the outbreak of COVID-19 in the country. Therefore, it is pertinent that various short, medium and long term plans should be available as a tool to resuscitate the economy of Akwa Ibom State and Nigerian at large from the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic outbreak.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are made based on the findings of this study:

1. All precautionary measures put in place by government and relevant health bodies aimed at tackling COVID-19 should be obeyed and sustained.
2. Due to the fragile economic situation in Nigeria before the coronavirus pandemic, the country should not be subjected to total lockdown for so long. A partial lockdown should be adopted in order not to worsen the economic situation.

The partial lockdown of states should be reviewed from time to time, while markets and other small and medium scale enterprises should be allowed to open biweekly at least with a controlled influx of consumers. More loan should be given to businesses to help cushion the effects of COVID-19 on business organizations

3. People that stay at home should be sensitized on what to do to avoid developing mental health problem as a result of solitude. While social gatherings (physical contacts) should remain banned, online association and other means that will satisfy the entertainment needs of the people should be encouraged.

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